

Open Science NL

Open Research Software Advisory Panel

Meeting Agenda

12 December 2025, 15:00 – 17:00 CET

Location: MS Teams

Attendees

- Ana Martinovici
- Daniel S. Katz
- Daniela Gawehns
- John Swinbank
- Karthik Ram
- Laurents Sesink
- Martine de Vos
- Mateusz Kuzak
- Morane Gruenpeter
- Santosh Ilamparuthi
- Vincent Traag
- Mark van Assem - Acting Co-Chair
- Marta Teperek (MT) - Acting Chair

Apologies

- Thomas Pronk
- Maria Cruz, Chair

Agenda

15.00 - 15.05 – Welcome and agenda

- Minutes of the last meeting have been published on Zenodo:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17295508>

15.05 - 15.10 - Update on the implementation of the OSNL Work Programme 2024-2025

15.10 – 16.00 – [OSNL Work Programme 2026-2027](#)

- How we addressed your comments
 - First come, first served calls for proposals
- Any other questions
- Would any of you like to receive a printed version of the work programme?

16:00 – 16.10 – *Break*

16.10 - 16.50 – Advisory panel – going forward

There are two aspects pertaining to the advisory panel going forward which need to be discussed:

- Half of the members up for re-election (terms ends in April/May 2026)
- The Open Science NL Steering Board asked the panels for advice on whether, going forward, it is advisable to maintain separate FAIR Data and Open Research Software advisory panels, or whether - given the overlap in content and the potential synergies - it would be better to merge the two into a single advisory panel.

16.50 – 17.00

- OSNL Steering Board will decide on the way forward with the panels taking into account the advice of both panels. Outcome and the next steps (possible elections) will be communicated via email.
- Doodle poll will be sent out for a meeting in Q1 2026; subsequent meetings will be planned afterwards.